

Requirements Engineering for Data Products: Adapting User Stories

Referencias

- Alves, A. P. S., Villamizar, H., Kalinowski, M., Azevedo, K., Escovedo, T., & Lopes, H. (2024). Industrial Practices of Requirements Engineering for ML-Enabled Systems in Brazil (SBES'24) <https://www-di.inf.puc-rio.br/~kalinowski/publications/AlvesKM24.pdf>
- Amirian, E., Abdollahzadeh, A., and N. Sulaiman. "Synergizing Hybrid Agile-Scrum and CRISP-DM (2024) Approaches in Data Science Project Management." Paper presented at the SPE Canadian Energy Technology Conference and Exhibition, Calgary, Alberta, Canada, March 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/218114-MS>
- Cordeiro, R., Alves, I., Alves, S., Goldman, A. (2024). Being Agile in a Data Science Project. In: Kruchten, P., Gregory, P. (eds) Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Programming – Workshops. XP XP 2022 2023. Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, vol 489. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48550-3_6
- Das, S. (2021). Agile Systems Engineering in Building Complex AI Systems. In: Lawless, W.F., Llinas, J., Sofge, D.A., Mittu, R. (eds) Engineering Artificially Intelligent Systems. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 13000. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-89385-9_12
- Halme, E., Jantunen, M., Vakkuri, V., Kemell, K.-K., & Abrahamsson, P. (2024). Making ethics practical: User stories as a way of implementing ethical consideration in Software Engineering. *Information and Software Technology*, 167, 107379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2023.107379>
- Kraut, N., & Transchel, F. (2022). On the Application of SCRUM in Data Science Projects. 2022 7th International Conference on Big Data Analytics (ICBDA), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICBDA55095.2022.9760341>
- Romao, L., Villamizar, H., Oliveira, R., Alonso, S., & Kalinowski, M. (2025). Agile Management for Machine Learning: A Systematic Mapping Study. *En Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA 2025) (LNCS 16082)*, pp. 350–360. Springer. https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1007/978-3-032-04200-2_24